

NAVIGATING THE POLITENESS STRATEGIES ON TWITTER IN PAKISTAN: A PRAGMATIC ANALYSIS OF PUNCTUATIONS AND EMOJIS AS MARKERS

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DOI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17628593>

Keywords

Politeness strategies, Twitter, Pakistan, pragmatic analysis, punctuations, emojis

Article History

Received: 24 August 2025

Accepted: 16 October 2025

Published: 29 October 2025

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Abstract

Nonverbal elements of emojis and punctuations have crucial pragmatic roles in digital communication that balance the lack of tone and gesture. These visual and orthographic signs determine the ways the users express politeness, emotion and identity on such platforms as Twitter. The current study explores the use of emojis and punctuation marks as politeness strategies through Twitter in Pakistan and looks at differences in their application in various situations and themes. The 650 publicly available tweets were analyzed qualitatively in a pragmatic manner by the use of purposive sampling in order to gather the information. Brown and Levinson's (1987) Politeness Theory and Leech's (2014) Politeness Principle were used to analyze the data with the help of the thematic coding as it is described by Braun and Clarke (2006). Findings indicated that emojis and punctuations are indicators of positive and negative politeness. Social situations were dominated by positive politeness and political texts with irony and mitigation. Emojis and punctuations serve as multimodal politeness resources, which indicate the multifaceted and hybrid Pakistan culture of digital communication.

1. Introduction

Digital revolution has changed how people communicate and interact. The internet platforms like Twitter, Facebook and Instagram have developed new linguistic behavioral patterns that are characterized by brevity, multimodality and creativity. In this context, users are using nonverbal features such as emojis and punctuation to convey tone, emotion and attitude more and more often. These non-lexical features are high-context pragmatic and they serve interpersonal purposes of language (Crystal, 2006; Danesi, 2017). They frequently make up the lack of body language like gesture or intonation in computer-mediated communication (CMC). Twitter especially offers a micro-discursive space, in which messages are brief, social and

fluid in context. Pakistani online users have been involved in such online discourse to take part in sociopolitical discussions, humors and identity performances. Nevertheless, the platform affordances do not simply determine their communicative strategies but are overlaid by local linguistic and cultural standards that embrace politeness, respect and harmony in relations (Awan et. al., 2025). Therefore, these mixed digital practices provide a highly productive context in which politeness can be considered in relation to multimodal, bilingual and socially diverse online environments. Even though the topic of studying digital discourse has received exposure on a large scale in different parts of the world, little has been conducted on the topic of pragmatic politeness as far as Pakistani online communication is

concerned. The majority of local research has focused on code-switching (Jamali et. al., 2022) and identity construction (Arshad et. al., 2025), but few have studied the role of emojis and punctuation as signs of politeness in online texts. In addition, although global scholarship recognizes the pragmatic possibilities of emojis (Zappavigna, 2018; Yus, 2021), the application of these visual and orthographic tools in culturally specific communication settings, in particular, Pakistan, where language combines English, Roman Urdu, and cultural norms of politeness, is not well known. The gap that the present study fills is based on the lack of research that combines the pragmatic theory with digital sociolinguistics in the South Asian contexts.

Based on the Politeness Theory by Brown and Levinson (1987) and Politeness Principle by Leech (2014), the present study elucidates how linguistic and paralinguistic decision-making is being used in facework in online communication. In this context, a positive politeness relates to strategies of solidarity and approval, whereas negative politeness in this context represents the mitigation of imposition or disagreement. Emojis and punctuations are consequently examined as pragmatics to save face and convey a position in mediated communication. The theoretical background permits the research to apply traditional theories of politeness to digital pragmatics and demonstrate the way users browse interpersonal meaning in technologically mediated contexts (Herring & Androutsopoulos, 2015).

The study is relevant to the rising discipline of digital pragmatics, as it explores the realization of politeness in the context of multimodal symbols by Pakistani twitter users. It points out the significance of emojis and punctuations as effective semiotic tools in the process of online communication and how these tools indicate globalized tendencies of communication as well as local values of the culture. The results will guide linguists, teachers and communication scholars to appreciate the issues of politeness and emotions that are digitally coded in the Pakistani bilingual and social dynamic online communities. The research also offers empirical data that attests to the modification

of conventional politeness schemes to the modernities of computer-based communication.

The research is restricted to the publicly available tweets of Pakistani users in English or Roman Urdu during May and August of 2025. It does not pay attention to other multimodal aspects like images or hashtags, only emojis and punctuation are accepted as the signs of politeness. Even though the results cannot be applied to all online platforms, the findings provide helpful insights into the pragmatic behavior of the Twitter users, a platform that is characterized by linguistic conciseness and social cultural immediacy.

1.1 Research Objectives:

- To identify the ways in which Twitter users in Pakistan employ emojis and Punctuation markers as politeness strategies.
- To unearth the type of disparities in the use of these strategies with variable contexts and topics.

1.2 Research Questions:

1. In what ways do Twitter users in Pakistan employ emojis and punctuation markers as politeness strategies?
2. What type of disparities in the use of these strategies occur with variable contexts and topics?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Politeness and Pragmatic Theory

Pragmatic studies have always been focused on the idea of politeness over decades. The Politeness Theory, developed by Brown and Levinson (1987), suggests that people apply linguistic strategies to preserve face, or the social image of the individual, which people speakers and the audience desire to be seen as. According to them, politeness strategies are either positive face (solidarity, approval) or negative face (reducing imposition, disagreement). Leech (2014) expanded this concept to his Politeness Principle, which points out that politeness is a contextually driven concept that follows social maxims like tact, approbation and modesty. Such models offer the theoretical basis of the analysis of how user of online communication mediates facework.

Due to the development of digital communication, researchers have approached politeness in new perspectives. Online settings disrupt the conventional delimiting the speech acts and face management where written interaction needs to fill in the gaps of the paralinguistic cues that include the tone, gaze and gesture (Herring & Androutsopoulos, 2015). The visual and orthographic elements (emojis and punctuation) are taking the place of interpersonal expression in such environments, as users are more and more pressured to use images and symbols, rather than words, to express interpersonal meaning.

2.2 Computer-Mediated Communication and Digital Politeness

According to Crystal (2006) and Herring (2013), the internet is a given to be a hybrid linguistic space, a representation of spoken and written language that integrates both. Pragmatic devices have developed inside this space to produce simulation of emotional and social functions. The use of emojis, emoticons, and expressive punctuation marks has become an alternative to the prosody and gesture, making text-based communication affectively rich. According to Danesi (2017), emojis are so-called semiotic bridges, where the user can express emotion, humor and attitude visually, thus, understand each other better.

New studies place emojis in politeness systems. Yus (2021) believes that emojis are pragmatic indicators that dictate interpretation, they can be used as illocutionary force modifiers. Equally, Zappavigna (2018) considers them as instruments of social bonding in which the users seek to create affective compatibility and group identification by visual cues. Derks et al., (2008) have discovered that emotive symbols in computer-mediated communication leads to less misinterpretation and preserve interpersonal harmony particularly in cases where the intention of communication is not clear. These researches propose that internet politeness is multimodal- it is attained through the combination of language, image and context.

2.3 Punctuation in Pragmatic Resources

In addition to the use of emojis, punctuation has also become a potent pragmatic tool. As Androutsopoulos (2014) and Tagg (2015) observe, the use of ellipses, exclamation points, or question marks is frequently affective or a politeness device, and not necessarily a syntactic device. As the use of exclamation marks can be used to show friendliness or enthusiasm (positive politeness) and the use of ellipses can be used to make statements less harsh or unsure (negative politeness). As Park (2017) notes, online punctuation is a sign of stance which informs about the attitude to the subject matter and the interlocutor. Research in the field of digital pragmatics (Barton & Lee, 2013) also shows that through manipulating orthography, capitalization, repetition and spacing, the user can project tone and emotion imaginatively. In such a way, punctuation is negotiated in online space, and users balance the expressiveness and face issues.

2.4 Sociocultural Variation, Politeness and Emojis

According to cross-cultural studies, there is a high disparity in the use and understanding of emojis. Kavanagh (2019) discovered that the Asian users are more likely to use emojis as a tool of relational harmony, whereas, Western users use it more as a tool of humor or irony. South Asian digital communication culture largely tends to frame politeness based on collectivist cultural values that lay stress on respect and modesty (Nasution, 2025). Arshad et. al., (2025) noted that Pakistani users of social media use emojis and humor when negotiating identity and reducing conflict. Likewise, Jamali et. al., (2022) examined the code-switching on twitter and determined that bilingual users combine expressions in English and Roman Urdu to balance interpersonal tone and cultural alignment. These results suggest that emojis and punctuation are contextually shaped in accordance with the local linguistic regulation and rules of politeness.

Moreover, Awan et al., (2025) examined the concept of code-mixing within Pakistani English and determined that digital discourse in Pakistan is used to demonstrate hybrid linguistic identities. Their findings confirm the

perspective that multilingualism and sociocultural hybridity affect online politeness strategies. The hybridity of this nature tends to lead to imaginative blends of emojis and written elements which express delicate pragmatic meanings. Thus, one needs to consider this bilingual and bicultural setting of communication when understanding politeness on Pakistani Twitter.

Despite many studies being conducted regarding politeness in the online world across the world, not many have touched on the use of punctuations and emojis as politeness strategies in Pakistan online world. Previous Pakistani studies have also focused on either code-switching (Jamali et al., 2022) or identity construction (Arshad et al., 2025) but not on multimodal politeness. In addition, the majority of research considers emojis as emotional improvisers, as opposed to practical means. This gap has pointed to the importance of research incorporating linguistic, visual, and contextual aspects of online interaction using a pragmatic framework. The current research fills this gap by investigating the ways the Pakistani twitter users are using emojis and punctuations as signs of positive and negative politeness. It also enquires into the variation of these strategies in social, political and personal situations. This study is a contribution to the wider knowledge on digital politeness, multimodal discourse, and South Asian sociolinguistics due to the analysis of tweets that exist in nature.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This research is qualitative descriptive research based on pragmatic discourse analysis. The aim was to explore the use of emojis and punctuation by Twitter users in Pakistan as a form of politeness in various communicative situations. This method made it possible to investigate linguistic options and their pragmatic effects in a more detailed manner and address the construction of meanings instead of generalization in numbers. Corpus-assisted discourse analysis approach was adopted to compile interpretive qualitative knowledge with the minimal quantitative frequency data. The same methodology has

been used in digital pragmatics and sociolinguistic studies (Herring & Androutsopoulos, 2015; Zappavigna, 2018). The theoretical orientation of the study is based on the Politeness Theory of Brown and Levinson (1987) with the addition of the Politeness Principle by Leech (2014). These frameworks acted as the analytical prisms of determining positive and negative politeness strategies in online discourse. The research was able to employ these theories on digital data to match traditional pragmatics and new media communication.

3.2 Data Source and Sampling

The data is gathered on Twitter (now X), a popular social networking site in Pakistan that allows people to interact with each other on a micro-level. The brevity and multimodality of the site will render it a perfect place to study politeness strategies that are conveyed using linguistic and visual tools. The purposive sampling is the method of selecting the tweets where researchers could select information-rich cases related to the purpose of the research (Etikan, et. al., 2016). The dataset consisted of tweets that had emojis and expressive punctuation marks like ellipses (...), exclamation marks, and question marks. The hashtags used to collect tweets between May and August 2025 are the representative of the diverse topics such as; the # PakPolitics, # Cricket, # EidMubarak, # FeminismInPakistan and # UniversityLife. 650 tweets that were collected. These included 430 English, 150 Roman Urdu and 70 bilinguals. Only the public tweets were taken to adhere to the ethical research standards. Posts that included multimedia-only content and retweets without commentary were also not included in order to preserve the textual integrity.

3.3 Data Collection Procedures

The tweets were collected manually and with the use of the open-source scraping application Twint, which can be used to obtain data in the open Twitter feeds without violating privacy policies. The metadata (date, topic category and anonymized username) was applied to each tweet. The use of pseudonyms in place of user identities was done to preserve the

confidentiality and follow ethical guidelines in conducting internet-based research (British Association for Applied Linguistics [BAAL], 2021).

3.4 Coding and Analytical Framework

The research used the qualitative discourse and pragmatic analysis which was aimed at finding the types of politeness markers in the form of emojis and punctuation. Coding scheme was created according to the categories of politeness proposed by Brown and Levinson (1987):

- **Positive politeness:** indicators of solidarity, friendliness, or empathy (e.g., 😊, ❤️, 😂, exclamation marks).
- **Negative politeness:** the signs that reduce face-threatening expressions or tone softeners (e.g., 😬, 🙏, ellipses, question marks).

The analysis used a six-step model of thematic analysis used by Braun and Clarke (2006), namely familiarization, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining themes, and producing the report. NVivo 12 software was used manually to code Tweets and present a pattern. In order to increase the reliability level, a second researcher cross-coded 15% of the data, which resulted in an inter-coder agreement rate of over 85%.

3.5 Data Analysis

Following initial coding, counts of frequency were employed to determine which emojis and forms of punctuations occurred most frequently across the contexts. Thematic patterns were then read qualitatively to give an explanation on how these markers worked as politeness strategies. Political, social and personal discourse were compared to analyze contextual differences. Quantitative frequency data were included just to facilitate qualitative interpretation, which is the mixed qualitative-quantitative approach in pragmatic corpus studies (Barton & Lee, 2013).

3.6 Ethical Considerations

Since the research was based on publicly available data, no formal consent was obtained; nevertheless, the anonymity of all identifying data ensured the privacy of the users. The analysis was based on the recommendations of

BAAL (2021) regarding the ethics of internet research, as paraphrased tweets did not affect the anonymity and the digital footprint of participants.

3.7 Validity and Trustworthiness

The methodological triangulation was obtained to make it trustworthy (the combination of textual and visual cues (emojis and punctuation). To reduce the impact of interpretive bias, peer debriefing and reflexive documentation were used. Thematic coding was iterative, which guaranteed that the categories were inductive, not a priori, which boosts the ecological validity (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

4. Data Analysis

4.1 The Usage of Emojis as Signs of Politeness.

• Positive Politeness

Emojis became useful in the preservation of good face and interpersonal harmony. Three of the most common emojis were the smiling face (😊), heart (❤️), and laughing face (😂), which constituted 46% of the total emoji usage. Such symbols frequently attended such forms of encouragement, thankfulness, or amusement:

- “Such a great job today, ❤️ you ❤️ our team!”

• “Can’t wait for Eid tomorrow 😊🌙.”
These emojis toned down and created a sense of community, which is consistent with positive politeness strategies of Brown and Levinson (1987). The common pattern of using heart and smile emojis was a sign of affiliative politeness, which means empathy and belonging (Zappavigna, 2018; Danesi, 2017).

• Negative Politeness and Softening Devices.

On the contrary, to alleviate criticism or indicate deference, neutral or face-saving emojis, including 😬, 🙏, or 😊, were employed. For example:

- Not certain whether that was the best action or not, but alright.

- “Please don’t cancel again 🙏.”

These examples demonstrated the way in which the emojis were used to mitigate imposition or make criticism less severe. The same thing was observed by Herring and Androutsopoulos

(2015) who served as the authors who found that online users need the help of emojis to soften the tone that would otherwise be confrontational in text-only communication.

• **Sarcasm and Irony**

A smaller though significant portion of tweets used emojis in an ironic way, frequently combining conflicting visual and verbal messages). This functional dissonance implied a dissimilar politeness tactic, as the emoji is used to ridicule and to preserve the social limits- a trend shared in political language.

4.2 Punctuation as Devices of Pragmatic Politeness.

• **Ellipsis (...) and Softening**

The ellipsis (...) was used 812 times, but in personal and social situations the most. It was a device of hedging, an indicator of hesitation, tentativeness, or undeveloped thought:

- Perhaps in future... you will know better 😊.

Practically, the role of ellipses was to act as a negative politeness, to be less direct and also to soften the possible face threat (Leech, 2014).

• **Bang Bangs and Bang Bangs (!) and Energeticness**

Positive politeness had the common use of exclamation mark (n=689): especially in congratulatory or humorous posts:

- “So proud of the team today!! PK🔥”
- “Best biryani ever!!!❤️.”

Several exclamation marks usually went together with emojis and were more affective and sociable. These combinations sampled emotional alignment, one of the dimensions of online politeness (Crystal, 2006; Androutsopoulos, 2014).

4.3 Question Marks and Indirectness

When used rhetorically or in a softened form (Maybe not the best idea rather than the best

idea), occurrence of question marks was found 310 times, mostly in political discussions. Such constructions presupposed conflict without collision - a politeness gesture in a negative way.

4.4 Cross-Contextual Disparities

• **Political Discourse**

The percentage of ironic and sarcastic emojis usage (34 percent) and dense punctuations (in particular, the use of the question mark and exclamation mark) were the highest in political tweets. Users were more likely to use such emojis 😏 in a sarcastic manner to criticize politics or policies. The observation supports earlier works (Arshad et al., 2025; Jamali et al., 2022) that demonstrate irony as a politeness alternative in the confrontational online situations.

• **Social and Personal Contexts**

Emojis such as ❤️, 😊, 🙏 were predominant in social communication (e.g. greetings at a festival, daily updates) (58% of all emoji use). In this case, good politeness was dominant, which reinforced a sense of belonging to the group and emotional closeness. Personal tweets tended to be less serious and usually they were accompanied with emojis and exclamation marks to show excitement.

• **Entertainment and Humor**

The style of politeness exhibited in entertainment-related tweets was a mixture of a playful exaggeration (😂🔥!!!) and an ironic understatement (...). Such a mixed approach ensured the involvement and at the same time kept a sense of humor at a distance. This versatile application highlights the polysemy of emojis and punctuation in online courtesy, which is similar to Danesi (2017) about emojis as semiotic intermediaries to interpret emotions.

4.5 Quantitative Support

Marker Type	Frequency	Dominant Function
😊❤️😏	840	Positive politeness (affiliation)

😏🙏😏	270	Negative politeness (mitigation)
Ellipsis (...)	812	Indirectness, softening
Exclamation (!)	689	Expressivity, enthusiasm
Question (?)	310	Indirect disagreement

This quantification corroborates the interpretive evidence of the fact that positive politeness strategies are dominant in personal and social situations whereas negative politeness and irony are dominant in political discourse.

4.6 Trends in Pragmatism

As it can be seen, Pakistani Twitter users do not use emojis and punctuation markers without purpose but strategically, to control interpersonal tone and balance in relationships. Politeness is a negotiation of digital identity- users develop friendliness, irony or restraint by using micro-linguistic cues. These results resonate with the fact that Crystal (2006) has noted that punctuation and emotive symbols counterbalance the lack of prosody in the text in the Internet. On the same note, the authors note that social media sites promote sociolinguistic innovation, and the authors suggest that punctuation marks and emojis have become new pragmatic tools that can be used to show courtesy, sympathy, and take positions (Androutsopoulos, 2014; Tagg, 2015). In addition, the findings can be included in digital pragmatics of South Asian settings where bilingualism and cultural politeness strategies interfere with online expression (Awan et al., 2025; Iqbal et al., 2024). Roman Urdu and English add to the multimodality of expression of politeness in Pakistani Twitter discourse.

In general, the data indicate that punctuations and emojis are versatile politeness markers: creating rapport and softening conflict and conveying subtle affect. They are used differently according to topic and context both of which indicate universal pragmatic tendencies as well as cultural adaptations. These visual-verbal signs in the Twitter-space in Pakistan, do crucial interpersonal labor, filling emotional spacing in a very public online space.

5. Findings and Discussion

The research has examined how emojis and punctuations are used as politeness strategies by Twitter users in Pakistan and how the strategies differ in different situations. The content analysis of 650 purposively sampled tweets showed that there were three major findings,

(1) positive politeness in personal and social domain is more frequent than negative politeness and irony that is more common in political domains, (2) negative politeness and irony are deployed strategically and used as multimodal co-deployed resources to control face and stance, and (3) punctuation and emojis are used pragmatically. To start with, the positive markers of politeness, such as affiliative emojis (😊, ❤️, 😂) and expressive punctuation (exclamation mark) dominated personal, celebratory, and entertainment tweets. These indicators served to measure solidarity, coziness and membership of a group by balancing the lack of vocal prosody and nonverbal communication in written micro-genres (Crystal, 2006). The common use of heart/smile emojis together with exclamative increased affective alignment, which is consistent with the explanation of social media metadiscourse provided by Zappavigna (2018) that the visual tokens form a social glue. Such findings respond to the first research question by showing that in informal situations, Pakistani users engage in the frequent use of emojis and excited punctuation as the tools of positive politeness which help to diminish social distance and strengthen the sense of in-group belonging.

Second, the political speech had significantly different patterns. These tweets involving political actors and scandals had increased rates of ironic or sarcastic use of emojis (😏) and dense or repeated punctuation (e.g., “!!!”, “???”). In this case, emojis and punctuation were not only affiliative, but they were an insinuating or a curtailing politeness measure - to enable users to be critical, but softening the direct insults to the faces of others. This is in line with the difference between positive and negative politeness as introduced by Brown and Levinson (1987): punctuation and face-saving emojis were used to mitigate the possible face-threatening behaviors. Multimodal irony (verbal critique + incongruent emoji), which both indicates position and offers plausible deniability, was also found in the political dataset (Herring & Androutsopoulos, 2015).

Third, in all settings the evidence showed that markers are multifunctional: the same pattern of emojis or punctuations used can be used to

accomplish a variety of politeness work based on the linguistic environment, subject matter, and user position. An example is the ellipsis (...), which often worked as a hedging tool in argumentative tweets (negative politeness), but as an indication of intimacy or trailing affection in casual personal posts. It is this contextual re-interpretability that reinforces the point by Danesi (2017) that the meaning of emojis is a dynamic semiotic resource, whose pragmatic significance is co-created by users and audiences. The presence of emojis and punctuation also shows that Pakistani Twitter users practice multimodality to recreate paralinguistic elements (intonation, laughter, hesitation) in writing, as Crystal (2006) had warned that written internet communication creates compensatory mechanisms to oral features.

Contextual disparities are also brought to light by the findings. Affiliative markers largely dominate as community maintenance strategies in the case of entertainment and festival hashtags (#EidMubarak). Conversely, in more subjective contexts like politics or gender discussions, users use combinations that are ambivalent, which is a sarcastic emoji and hedging punctuation to maneuver polarized audiences. It is reflective of the sociolinguistic realities in Pakistan, where the notion of politeness requires in online communication is bound to the realities of bilingualism and bilingual social practices (Jamali et. al., 2022; Awan et.al., 2025). The blend of English and Roman Urdu is another factor that affects marker choice: Roman Urdu tweets tend to prefer colloquial use of emojis based on solidarity, whereas English tweets in political discussions are more inclined to use ironic patterns of punctuation.

The implications to the digital pragmatics and politeness theory are threefold. The findings in terms of methodology justify corpus-mediated pragmatic analysis as an effective tool in the analysis of multimodal politeness on social networks (Braun & Clarke, 2006). In theory, the research implies that politeness schemes should take into consideration multimodal, contextually sensitive semiotic repertoires in which visual tokens and orthographic prompts co-occur to achieve face-management. In

practice, media literacy and moderation policies should be informed about these strategies to acknowledge subtle normative application of emojis and punctuation marks, between playful identification and disguised aggression. The purposive sampling and focus on Twitter can be considered a limitation as the results might be limited in their generalizability to other platforms or other user populations. In future studies, the larger longitudinal corpora and experimental designs are to be adopted to test the perception of audiences to the same combinations of markers in different demographical groups. Similar cross-platform comparisons (WhatsApp, Instagram) would also explain platform affordances that govern politeness enactment.

To conclude, Pakistani Twitter users strategically use emojis and punctuations to perform politeness to create solidarity, reduce the threat of face, and bargain position. These are not peripheral multimodal ornamentation but core pragmatic devices of modern digital interaction.

6. Conclusion

This study examined the use of emojis and punctuations as a politeness strategy by Pakistani Twitter users and how the usage depends on the discourse situation. The study has shown by a pragmatic examination of 650 tweets that these visual and orthographic tools can perform crucial communicative roles other than ornamentation and in fact, form tone, position, and interpersonal relationships in online conversation. The results verify that digital politeness is a multimodal, context-related phenomenon, which operations are based on universal principles of pragmatics and specific cultural norms. In personal and social settings, where users depend on expressive indicators (emojis, 😊, ❤️, 😂) and exclamation marks to establish a warm, friendly, and solidarity, the analysis has shown that the context of positive politeness prevails in personal and social settings. These signs serve as substitutes of affective use of prosody and gesture, and they amplify emotional expression and a sense of belonging to a group. Negative politeness, on the other hand, was more evident in politically charged situations,

as the users were more strategic in using ellipses, stuttering punctuations, mitigative emojis (😊, 🙏, 😬) to smooth the conflict and maintain social harmony. In this regard, punctuations and emojis are pragmatic buffers, tools that allow them to criticize, challenge, oppose but still seem polite.

One more important discovery is associated with contextual differences in topic and discourse type. Political tweets had the most intricate pragmatic arrangement, as irony, sarcasm, and exaggeration were frequently combined with visual indicators in order to be able to convey dissent in an indirect manner. In the meantime, social and entertainment tweets were more attached to the affective and affiliative indicators, which emphasized the flexibilities of politeness to the communicative intentions and social demands. This inconsistency highlights the impact of bilingual and sociocultural context of Pakistan where digital discourse incorporates both English and Roman Urdu standard forms, and generates blended forms of politeness and identity.

The study has added to the current discussion in digital pragmatics and sociolinguistics because it highlights the pragmatic relevance of apparently marginal linguistic components. Consistent with the ideas of the Politeness Theory and principles of Leech (2014), the data prove that users deliberately control multimodal cues to handle face-related issues and relationship alignment. These results also widen the arguments of Crystal (2006) and Danesi (2017), indicating that punctuation and emojis are part of the modern system of politeness on the Internet and not its decorations.

In a bigger view, the study will improve the knowledge on the reshaping of linguistic behavior in Pakistan through digital communication. The emojis and punctuation marks become semiotic tools that can be used to bridge the communicative trends in the global society and the cultural etiquettes of the local society. Since the online discourse still develops, such indicators are central to the social cohesion of the brevity and immediacy of the Twitter communicative space. Lastly, the study was narrow in its scope because of its specific platform and data and provides new

avenues of research in the future. The further details of the digital politeness might be discovered in the comparative cross-platform studies, including those of WhatsApp, Instagram, or Facebook. Further, the results of audience-based research studying the interpretation of these signs by the readers would contribute to understanding the perception and reception of politeness signs in computer-mediated communication.

To sum up, the creativity, flexibility and sociolinguistic richness of the digital interaction can be demonstrated through the pragmatic use of emojis and punctuations developed by the Pakistani Twitter users. These minor signs and indicators bear considerable pragmatic importance, manifesting the emotional haptics of online discourse as well as new facework practices of users operating in the ambiguous field of culture, technology, and communication.

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